

IN THE 60S OF THE 20TH CENTURY, UZBEKISTAN'S RELATIONS WITH THE COUNTRIES OF THE AFRICAN CONTINENT IN THE FIELD OF COTTON PRODUCTION

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Abstract: In this article, the efforts to gain national independence in the countries of the African continent, the economic development after independence and the relations of Uzbekistan with the countries of the African continent in the direction of cotton production, historical literature and materials in the periodical press are presented explained based on.

Key words: Orjenikidze, Asia-Africa Economic Cooperation Organization, United Arab Republic, Senegal, Ghana, agriculture.

The 60s of the 20th century saw great changes in world politics. In the countries of the African continent, efforts to gain national independence have begun, and colonial empires are crumbling. first of all, European countries began to break socio-economic relations with colonial countries such as England and France. Also, the fact that the USA is an ally of the European imperialist countries has encouraged many African countries that have gained independence to maintain a distance in economic and diplomatic relations with the USA. In this political situation, many African countries that gained freedom saw the former USSR as their main partner in socio-economic relations.

After the Bandung conference of developing countries in 1955, relations of the former USSR with these countries developed at various levels. The Uzbek SSR was in second place in the former union after the Russian Federation in terms of economic relations with the union of these states. Because Uzbekistan's experience of planting cotton and other crops and getting a good harvest from them has begun to be studied in the production based on agriculture. It can be seen that the visit of the General Secretary of the Asia-Africa Economic Cooperation Organization Muhammad Ali Rifoat to the Uzbekistan SSR in December 1961 was aimed at inspecting the enterprises related to the agricultural sector. The honored guest visited "Tashselmash" factory, Smarqand tea packaging factory. Also, he visited the "Kyzil Uzbekistan" collective farm in the Orjenikidze district (1930-1992, now known as Qibray) of the Tashkent

region and met with growers¹. At that time, the cotton industry of Uzbekistan was considered one of the leaders in the world.

Since the climate of African countries is suitable for cotton cultivation, they often come to Uzbekistan to study modern and advanced methods of cotton cultivation. The delegation led by Lieutenant General Ibrahim Abdud (1900-1983), the Chairman of the Supreme Council of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Sudan and the Prime Minister of the Republic of Sudan, which arrived in July 1961, went to the collective farm named "Lenin" in Yangiyol district. In the spring of 1961, collective farmers planted cotton on a total of 2,855 hectares of land, and reported that they could harvest at least 30 centners from each piece of land as a result of their labor, cotton processing with mechanization, and the methods specified in scientific recommendations. The Minister of Agriculture, Irrigation and Hydroelectricity of Sudan, Makka Almana, visited the Central Asian branch of the All-Union Research Institute of Plant Science and got acquainted with the selection work being carried out there².

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Бельгийци не уходят из Конго // Правда Востока 26 август, 1960 года, № 198. (11173).
2. Благодарность Советскому правительству // Правда Востока 7 август, 1960 года, № 182. (11157).
3. Винокуров Ю.Н., Орлова А.С., Субботин В.А. История Заира в новое и новейшее время - М.: Наука. Главная редакция восточной литературы, 1982. - 311 с.
4. Винокуров Ю.Н. Политическая борьба в демократической Республике Конго (1965 - 2001 гг.) Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени доктора исторических наук. Москва-2005. – 32 с.
5. Вольнения в Конго. // Правда Востока 14 мая, 1960 года, № 112 (11087).
6. Денисова Т., Костелянец С. Бенин: Политические метаморфозы(К 60-летию независимости). // Азия и Африка сегодня 2020 № 12. – С. 38-45.
7. Заявление советского правительства. // Правда Востока 2 август, 1960 года, № 178. (11153).
8. Kenjayev, Sardor Nurmurod Son. "Amir Temur's Ambassadorial Activity in Diplomatic Relations with China (Min State)(In the Case of Fu An)." Miasto Przyszłości 29 (2022): 112-114.

¹ O'zbekiston savdo palatasining mehmoni (O'zTAG) // Qizil O'zbekiston 31dekabr, 1961yil, № 301. (12050).

² Ibrohim Abbudning O'zbekistonda bo'lishi (O'zTAG) // Qizil O'zbekiston 22 iyul, 1961yil, № 170. (11919).

9. Norboyev, Sardor Qavmiddinovich. "O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SIYOSIY PARTIYALARNING SIYOSIY VA IJTIMOY AHAMIYATI." Scientific progress 4.5 (2023): 4-8.
10. ERKINOVICH, TUYEV FAZLIDDIN. "FACTORS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN BUKHARA REGION IN 1991-1995 AND THE ISSUE OF PARTICIPATION IN FOREIGN RELATIONS." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.05 (2022): 256-258.
11. Shokirov, Mubin. "Tarixiy jarayonni bilish methodlari asosida analiz qilish." ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz) 5.5 (2021).
12. Urazov, Bobir. "A O'razov Bobir Baxtiyorovich: РУМИЙ-СЎФЕЙЛИК ТАРИҚАТИ ПЕШВОСИ." Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti journal 2.2 (2022).
13. Sharipov, Abduxakimjon. "A SOCIAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF GENDER POTENTIAL: SOCIAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF GENDER POTENTIAL." Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti journal 2.2 (2022).
14. Rajabov, Alisher, and Shoxijahon Urunov. "XVII ASRNING 1-HALF BUXORO XONLIGINING SIYOSIY INQIROZI VA UNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI." Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences 2.5 (2023): 51-54.
15. Togayeva, Dilnoza. "WORD OF VARIABILITY IN UZBEK LANGUAGE." Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences 1.9 (2021): 454-458.
16. Kilichev, Rajab Ergashovich. "BUKHARA IS THE ANCIENT CITY OF THE EAST." Theoretical & Applied Science 7 (2020): 26-28.
17. Boboqulov, Oxunjon. "SHAROF RASHIDOVNING AFRO-OSIYO XALQLARI BIRDAMLIGI CONFERENCES DA ISHTIROKI XUSUSIDA." Innovation and development: theory and practice 2.17 (2023): 187-189.
18. Рахматова, Холidahon. "ХОЖА АХРОР ВАЛИЙНИНГ ТИНЧЛИК, ОСОЙИШТАЛИК ВА НАМЎНАТЛИККА ДОИР Г 'OLIVES-BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT OMILI ADJECTIVE." Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муамолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-governmental issues/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. 3.S/5 (2023).
19. Murtozayev, Shahobiddin. "ABU HAFS UMAR SUHRAVARDIY INSON NAFSINI ANGLASHGA DOIR FALSAFIY QARASHLARINING TAHLILI." Scientific journal of the Fergana State University 1 (2023): 53-53.

20. MZ Orziyev, OAOGL Boboqulov. “ Amir Temur va temuriylar davrida Buxoro shahri taraqqiyotiga oid” . Science and Education 3 (10), 540-544.
21. ATO Teshayev, O Boboqulov. “TURKISTONDA YANGI USUL MAKTABLARINING FAOLIYATI (XIX ASR OXIRI-XX ASR BOSHLARI)”. Scientific progress 2 (3), 269-275.
22. ATO Teshayev, O Boboqulov. “YANGI USUL MAKTABLARIDA DINIY VA DUNYOVIY FANLARNING O’QITILISHI (IS’HOQXON IBRAT VA MUNAVVARQORI TASHKIL ETGAN MAKTABLAR MISOLIDA)” Scientific progress 2 (3), 276-283.
23. O Бабакулов. “MUSTAQIL KONGO DAVLATINING SSSR BILAN DIPLOMATIK ALOQALARI (davriy matbuot gazetalari tahlili asosida)” ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ.
24. BO Axmat o'g'li. “OSIYO VA AFRIKA XALQLARI BIRDAMLIK TASHKILOTIDA O'ZBEKLARNING ISHTIROKI”
25. BO Axmadovich. “HOMER DOSTONLARI TARIXIY MANBA SIFATIDA O’RGANILISHI” . Journal of new century innovations 28 (2), 133-139.
26. O Boboqulov. “THE PROBLEM OF MALNUTRITION AMONG YOUNG CHILDREN ON THE AFRICAN CONTINENT AND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VARIOUS INFECTIOUS DISEASES IN THE REGION”. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD 2 (4), 106-117.
27. O Boboqulov. “OA Temuriylar davrida Buxoro shahri taraqqiyoti”. Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali 2.
28. OA Boboqulov. “Socio-Economic Life During the Reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids (In the Example of the City of Bukhara)”. Miasto PrzyszłościKielce.

